

Multiculturalism in Organizations

Multiculturalidade nas Organizações
Multiculturalidad en las Organizaciones

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Abstract:

Multiculturalism in organizations refers to the diversity of cultures, ethnicities, languages and perspectives within the work environment. This article addresses how the presence of multiple cultures can positively impact innovation, creativity and problem-solving in companies, while promoting greater adaptability in the market. The article also highlights the challenges that arise, such as communication barriers, possible cultural conflicts and the need for effective management of this diversity to avoid exclusion or marginalization of minority groups.

Keywords: *Culture; Interculturality; Multiculturalism; Organizations.*

Resumo:

A multiculturalidade nas organizações refere-se à diversidade de culturas, etnias, línguas e perspectivas dentro do ambiente de trabalho. O presente artigo aborda como a presença de múltiplas culturas pode impactar positivamente a inovação, a criatividade e a solução de problemas nas empresas, ao mesmo tempo em que promove uma maior adaptabilidade no mercado. O artigo também destaca os desafios que surgem, como as barreiras de comunicação, possíveis conflitos culturais e a necessidade de uma gestão eficaz dessa diversidade para evitar exclusão ou marginalização de grupos minoritários.

Palavras-chave: *Cultura; Interculturalidade; Multiculturalidade; Organizações.*

Resumen:

La multiculturalidad em las organizaciones se refiere a la diversidad de culturas, etnias, idiomas y perspectivas dentro del entorno laboral. Este artículo aborda cómo la presencia de múltiples culturas puede impactar positivamente em la innovación, la creatividad y la resolución de problemas em las empresas, al tiempo que promueve una mayor adaptabilidad em el mercado. El artículo también destaca los desafíos que surgem, como las barreras de comunicación, los posibles conflictos culturales y la necesidad de una gestión eficaz de esta diversidad para evitar la exclusión o marginación de los grupos minoritarios.

Palabras clave: *Cultura; Interculturalidad; Multiculturalidad; Organizaciones.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Human Resources Management is a strategic area within companies. It is responsible for managing, allocating, guiding, selecting, and developing employees' potential within the organization. Its role is fundamental to proceeding with greater agility, efficiency, and effectiveness.

Diversity, by definition, involves a range of aspects, such as plurality and multiplicity. Therefore, it can be said that coexistence with people of different ages, ethnicities, genders, social and economic cultures, and sexual orientations—where everyone is unique—enriches precisely because of their particularity within the same environment.

Culture, in turn, encompasses the beliefs, habits, customs, and knowledge that make up everything everyone intrinsically possesses, adding value through the bonds created in society.

Organizational culture is directly linked to the company's purpose, beliefs, and values. Organizational climate refers to employees' feelings about the work environment, which, when healthy, generates several benefits for the company.

Inclusion in the job market means creating an environment that respects and values diversity. Inclusion means ensuring that people, regardless of race, gender, age, sexual orientation, or disability, are treated with respect and equality.

Cultural diversity within organizations brings both challenges and opportunities. On the one hand, cultural diversity can enrich creativity, innovation, and perspectives within the team, leading to more comprehensive and practical solutions to complex problems; on the other hand, it can cause discomfort and dissatisfaction due to a lack of information and empathy. Cultural differences can also lead to conflicts, misunderstandings, and communication barriers, harming team cohesion and performance.

Currently, companies are discussing the best way to address diversity, and to do so, they must address the multicultural environment within organizations. The central focus should be on integrating all employees into the company, creating a pleasant and enriching environment that values and enhances everyone's multicultural contributions, thereby fostering better adaptation and the exchange of experiences.

Multiculturalism has been gradually growing in the workplace and in daily life, but many challenges and difficulties remain. Why has this issue remained controversial or poorly resolved to this day?

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

As Godoy and Santos (2014, p. 20) maintain, the concept of Culture originated in France in the 18th century and soon spread into English and German. It was always followed by some complement, "culture of the arts," "culture of the sciences," and "organizational culture," as if it needed to be cultivated. Sometime later, it began to be used to designate the "formation," the "education" of the

spirit, and subsequently came to mean the act of instructing and then the state of mind cultivated by instruction (the state of an individual who possesses culture).

As stated by Lages and Matos (2009, p. 9), the concept of culture is used in a wide variety of contexts and has many meanings. The most common expressions are "traditional culture," "popular culture," and "mass culture," which have comprehensive meanings and differ little from one another.

The word has gained a definition synonymous with citizenship, not only in the scientific field, but also in everyday language.

Wagner (2018, p. 36) emphasizes that culture has become a way of talking about man and his particularities when viewed from a particular perspective. The term "culture" is a way of reducing human actions and purposes to the most basic level of significance, to examine universal terms and, in some sense, understand them.

The 1982 UNESCO Mexico City Declaration on Cultural Policies states that culture is:

The set of distinctive spiritual and material, intellectual and affective traits that characterize a society or social group, encompassing, in addition to the arts and letters, ways of life, fundamental human rights, value systems, traditions and beliefs (UNESCO 2001, p. 2, our translation).

Culture can be defined in many ways: customs, beliefs, actions, creations, thoughts, among others. The organizational environment is no different; every company has its own particularities, where everyone contributes with their way of being, knowing, and acting. What makes a difference is incorporating everyone's ideas into a project where they can express their thoughts, creatively innovate, and devise a plan.

Following Chiavenato's line of reasoning (2014, p. 153), organizational culture involves a "set of habits and beliefs established through norms, values, attitudes, and expectations shared by all members of the organization. Culture reflects the prevailing mindset in an organization (our translation)."

Everyone has different ideas and concepts, and by combining thoughts, they can generate innovative projects. Culture is an important aspect where there is no right or wrong; when we come together, we become capable of achieving or even surpassing our goals. Everyone's objective should be the same: a single goal and many minds thinking together towards concrete achievement.

As claimed by the American Stephen P. Robbins, culture is determined in this way:

Culture is composed of a combination of characteristics that are born and preserved through communication and cooperation between individuals in a society. It can be understood that culture is transmitted over time and refers to a system of values distributed among the people of an organization, and that it differs from one organization to another (ROBBINS 2005 apud DE SOUZA 2021, our translation).

Human beings have their own unique qualities and contribute by bringing a new way of thinking to the corporate environment, always respecting individuality,

maintaining a healthy, respectful, competitive environment, and generating ideas and debates that can improve and enhance the development and application of ideas in projects where everyone collaborates for the greater good. This resourcefulness brings motivation and well-being to this environment.

Psychologist Edgar Henry Schein defines organizational culture as follows:

An organization's culture can be defined as a set of shared basic assumptions that the group of people involved in it have learned as they solve their problems of external adaptation and internal integration, which has worked well enough to be considered valid and, likewise, assimilated by new members as the correct way to perceive, think and feel in relation to problems (SCHEIN, 1992 apud DE SOUZA 2021, our translation).

On the other hand, multiculturalism refers to the coexistence and interaction of diverse cultures in the same space or society. This implies recognizing, respecting, and appreciating cultural differences, promoting exchange and dialogue among these cultures to enrich coexistence and mutual understanding. Multiculturalism goes beyond simple tolerance, seeking integration where cultural differences are celebrated and considered a positive contribution to society.

Multiculturalism is the presence of various cultures in a community. It values cultural plurality without concern for the political or historical ties between cultures, and places great responsibility on the place each culture occupies by tradition.

Interculturality is the interrelation of cultures within a single environment. It proposes equal appreciation and cultural pluralism. It connects groups from diverse cultures.

Cultural diversity is cultural identity, a hallmark of a group. It is the differentiation between the various cultures around the world, including language, traditions, cuisine, religion, and others. They possess characteristics specific to a group within a particular territory.

The terms multiculturalism and multiculturalism first appeared around 1941. Around the late 1960s and early 1970s, social and political debates began to take shape in countries such as Canada, Australia, the United Kingdom, and the United States. Issues concerning ethnic and cultural diversity began to emerge, and topics addressing integration, identity, coexistence, and racial ideology grew significantly, continuing into the contemporary period.

As maintained by Stuart Hall, a British Jamaican sociologist, there is a perception of what multiculturalism would be:

Multiculturalism is a qualifying term. It describes the social characteristics and governance problems that arise in any society in which different cultural communities coexist and strive to build ordinary lives while retaining something of their "original" identity. In contrast, the term "multiculturalism" is a noun. It refers to the strategies and policies adopted to govern or manage problems of diversity and multiplicity generated by multicultural societies (HALL, 2003, p. 52, our translation).

Multiculturalism goes far beyond a word; it involves plurality, spontaneous

involvement in countries, and the pursuit of new public policies and strategies, and has become a reality, bringing with it a wide diversity. In one approach, Semprini (1999, p. 161, our translation) addresses the root of the word: "Multiculturalism is one of the fruits of the crisis of modernity. However, it is not limited to explaining the contradictions of the great ideals proposed by modernity."

In the same way that multiculturalism has resonated through new policies, Néstor García Canclini, an Argentinian anthropologist, offers another narrative that does not discard the others but instead uses the term to encompass various areas.

Multiculturalism, understood as a program that prescribes quotas for representation in museums, universities, and parliaments, as an undifferentiated exaltation of the successes and hardships of those who share the same ethnicity and gender, confines itself to the local level, without problematizing its insertion into complex social units on a large scale. (CANCLINI, 2004, p. 22 apud WEISSMANN 2018).

British sociologist Tariq Modood explains another concept that involves external characteristics, lived experiences, and integration. In accordance with him, multiculturalism is:

When integration processes are viewed in both directions, they function differently for different groups. In this understanding, each group is distinct, and integration cannot consist of a single pattern (hence the "multi"). "Culturalism" refers to the understanding that the groups in question should not be considered only by their novelty, their phenotype (visible aspect) or socioeconomic location, but by certain forms of group identity (MODOOD, 2005, p. 2 apud FERNANDES, 2010, p. 76, our translation).

Charles Taylor, a Canadian philosopher, has already highlighted the multicultural issue in the approach to societies, gradually reinforcing how much it is involved with social interactions, coexistence, beliefs, and especially integration, as stated by Taylor apud ANDRADE (2013, p. 90, our translation) "there is no doubt that societies are increasingly becoming multicultural, in the sense of including more than one cultural community that intends to survive".

Multiculturalism is interconnected with various cultures and spheres. Its scope is comprehensive, yet it often lacks a single, definitive definition. Still, it is always linked to integration, where many of these cultures and perspectives emerge. Several are not accepted everywhere, whether in a company, school, hospital, park, or other places where human interaction occurs, bringing ever more reflections and concepts.

It is noticeable that when discussing multiculturalism, the use of personal characteristics is quite prevalent, reflecting the idea that people possess their own cultures, religions, ethnicities, and viewpoints. Besides encountering these characteristics in daily life and across different countries, they are particularly noticeable in the professional sphere, where individuals with distinct differences are found.

In organizations, diversity is common both internally and externally;

nevertheless, even with this diversity, many challenges arise, such as difficulties in interpersonal relationships and the prevalence of prejudice. A closer analysis reveals the importance of multiculturalism in the workplace, highlighting how it provides a significant advantage and fosters growth, enabling dialogue that can overcome barriers and reach far beyond what one might initially perceive.

As claimed by Paiva in his article "Organizational Culture in Multicultural Organizations," he mentions what a multicultural organization would be, according to Canen and Canen:

It is said that institutions, their assumptions, and their dynamics are constructions of human groups in specific societies, inspired by unique cultural values, intimately linked to economic and political interests. A multicultural organization is understood as one in which individuals from different cultural perspectives work and in which its activities are articulated to this plurality, taking it into account in the very process of building the organizational culture, resulting in better business performance. A multicultural organization should encourage and value cultural differences (CANEN and CANEN 2005 apud PAIVA 2012, p. 10).

Currently, in a period of ever-increasing pursuit of evolution and innovation, diversity is present across all areas of life, becoming essential and driving the diversification of knowledge. These differences are significant for broadening perspectives in the organizational world, enabling growth in relationships, structures, stakeholders, and the company's market positioning. Another relevant factor is how the public today is beginning to view companies within their social context. Regarding minority groups, this is rarely discussed, but a more empathetic perspective is gradually emerging.

As claimed by Cox and Blake (1991 apud ARAÚJO 2022, p.81, our translation), "they also described how cultural heterogeneity in companies and the variety of perspectives facilitates the decision-making process, since multiple perspectives lead to better decisions".

Considering different types of people in an environment can lead to internal conflicts. Nevertheless, with good people management that not only integrates diverse individuals but also understands where each can contribute to harmony at work through knowledge sharing, perspectives, decision-making, productivity, and the quality of services provided, one can appreciate the importance of multiculturalism and its effective organizational management.

3. METHOD

Research conducted via online form, from October 1st to October 23rd, 2024, with 23 professionals in the field of Human Resources Management, from companies in various sectors, located in the State of São Paulo, aged between 25 and 65 years old, of both sexes.

All data obtained through the questionnaire were tabulated and analyzed using the form, Word tables (2021), and Excel graphs (2021).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research results, along with an analysis of the information obtained, will be presented below.

Chart 1 – Age:

Source: Authors 2024

Chart 2 - Gender:

Source: Authors 2024

Chart 3 – In which region do you reside?

Source: Authors 2024

The graphs above reflect the general characteristics of the research sample, with 39% of respondents being between 36 and 45 years old, mostly 52% male and

48% female, 87% residing in the east zone, 9% in the south zone and 4% in the west zone of São Paulo – SP.

Chart 4 – What position do you hold?

Source: Authors 2024

Chart 5 – How many employees are there in the company?

Source: Authors 2024

Graphs 4 and 5 show that 26% of respondents are managers, 30% are managers, supervisors, and coordinators, and 13% are others. Regarding the number of employees in the companies, 43% have between 5 and 15 employees, 17% between 16 and 30, 9% between 46 and 60, 4% between 31 and 45, and 26% have more than 60 employees.

The chart below shows that most companies have no foreign employees. Most companies reported having no foreign employees (74%), indicating a low level of international workforce diversity. Between 1 and 3 (9%) and more than 10 (9%) both have the same percentage, suggesting that some companies have few foreign employees, while others have a significant number. Between 4 and 6 (4%) and between 7 and 10 (4%) are the least represented categories, indicating that few companies have an intermediate number of foreigners on their teams.

Chart 6 – How many foreign employees does your company currently have?

Source: Authors 2024

Chart 7 – How many Black employees are part of the company?

Source: Authors 2024

As shown in the graph, 47.5% of companies have 1 to 5 Black employees, 21.8% have more than 20, 12.9% have 11 to 20, and 8.9% have 6 to 10, with no Black employees at all. This shows that companies hire very few people of African descent, and that this number is very high in proportion to the number of Black employees they have.

Chart 8 – How many employees are people with disabilities?

Source: Authors 2024

The graph shows the number of employees with disabilities (PWDs). Most companies (57% of cases) have no PWD employees. 26% of companies have 1-3 PWD employees, 13% have 10+ PWD employees, and 4% have 7-10 PWD employees.

Most companies still do not have employees with disabilities, which indicates a possible lack of inclusion and diversity in the workplace. The small number of companies with more than 10 employees with disabilities suggests that there is room to improve the integration of people with disabilities into the labor market, promoting greater accessibility and inclusive opportunities.

Chart 9 – What percentage of women hold leadership positions?

Source: Authors 2024

As shown in the graph, the highest concentration is in the "Up to 25%" range, indicating that most organizations have a low percentage of women in leadership positions. Next, we have the "More than 50%" range, which also has a significant number of occurrences. The intermediate ranges, "Between 25% and 50%" and "0%", show the lowest frequency.

Although some companies have more than 50% women in leadership positions, a significant proportion have less than 25%. This points to an imbalance in the distribution of women in leadership positions, suggesting the need for stronger inclusion and gender-equality policies to increase female participation in senior roles within organizations.

Chart 10 – How do you perceive the influence of cultural diversity in the workplace?

Source: Authors 2024

Very positive (43.4%), most respondents consider the influence of cultural diversity to be very positive, indicating that they believe diversity contributes significantly to the work environment.

A considerable proportion of respondents (39.4%) also perceive cultural diversity positively, reinforcing the view that it brings benefits. A smaller number of respondents

have a neutral perception (17.2%), which may indicate indifference or the view that cultural diversity does not directly impact the work environment.

Chart 11 – How often do you notice cultural conflicts in your company?

Source: Authors 2024

The graph shows how frequently employees perceive cultural conflicts in their companies. Most respondents indicate that these conflicts are “Rarely” perceived, accounting for 43% of responses. Next, 26% observe these conflicts “Occasionally,” while 22% state that they are “Frequent.” Only 9% of participants reported never witnessed cultural conflicts. This suggests that, although not a constant occurrence, cultural conflicts are still present in companies, with a significant portion of respondents reporting them on an occasional or frequent basis.

Chart 12 – What are the main challenges related to multiculturalism that you observe in the company?

Source: Authors 2024

It is evident that 27.8% of respondents say that differences in communication and conflicts over values and beliefs are the most prominent barriers to multiculturalism in companies. Differences in communication styles and divergent cultural values hinder understanding and collaboration between employees from different backgrounds.

Difficulty with team integration (27.8%) indicates that, despite diverse cultures, integrating team members into cohesive, collaborative teams is challenging.

Inequality of opportunity (8.3%) and I do not perceive challenges (8.3%) suggest that some respondents perceive problems related to equity, while others do not perceive challenges related to multiculturalism.

The graph indicates that multiculturalism is perceived as a challenge, especially in communication, cultural values, and team integration, while inequality of opportunity and perceived challenges have less impact among respondents.

Chart 13 – How can the company promote an inclusive and respectful environment?

Source: Authors 2024

The graph indicates that the vast majority believe in internal communication and policies. The research shows that 41% of managers believe that internal communication is the best way to promote this healthy environment, 31% believe that policies focused on diversity are the solution, 13% of the survey participants believe in educational lectures, 9% would use a selection process focused on inclusion and diversity, and 6% would form a diversity committee. In analysis, we can affirm that internal communication and educational policies are the best way to solve the issue.

This chart illustrates the main impacts of cultural diversity on innovation within the company. The most highlighted aspect is that "Cultural diversity within the company drives innovation," followed by "Ease of integrating different perspectives and experiences," with 8 and 6 responses, respectively.

A significant number of responses also valued an "Inclusive and culturally diverse environment," with 4 responses.

Finally, diversity is seen as a factor that "Stimulates creativity and more efficient problem-solving," with 3 (three) responses, placing less emphasis on it compared to the other aspects.

Chart 14 – How does cultural diversity impact innovation within the company?

Source: Authors 2024

5. CONCLUSION

According to field research with managers, coordinators, and supervisors, the number of foreigners in companies is low; approximately 74.5% of companies have no foreign employees. Another considerable number is Black employees, with only 1 to 5 in 47.5% of companies. Furthermore, regarding people with disabilities (PWDs), the percentage of companies is 57%.

Most respondents perceive the influence of diversity as positive, with cultural conflicts rarely occurring, partly because the current number of diverse and inclusive employees is small.

Even today, many do not consider multiculturalism relevant or have not analyzed it from this angle.

Therefore, the problem we face is challenging and complex. We see that many issues and attitudes have improved, but we are still far from the ideal level of equality, inclusion, and respect.

The issues surrounding the inclusion of people, whether they are people with disabilities, Black people, older people, LGBTQIA+ youth, or those with intellectual disabilities or impairments, demonstrate that there is still much prejudice and a lack of concern or interest in the matter.

Research has shown that for many, the issue of multiculturalism is irrelevant, and that many remain archaic, failing to evolve their thinking and critical sense. Though it is believed that change is possible if inclusion and interaction programs are implemented.

The topic is so complex that even research materials were difficult to find. However, there are still scholars passionate about organizational culture who advocate for and promote the benefits of inclusion.

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